

A Review on Natural Remedies for Mouth Ulcers: Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal gel

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ABSTRACT

Herbal medicine is more culturally acceptable, more compatible with the human body and has fewer adverse effects. The objective of the review is to formulate and evaluate herbal gel for mouth ulcer treatment. Numerous etiological variables can lead to the development of one of the most prevalent disorders mouth ulcers. No treatment for mouth ulcers may be considered fully effective, many numerous formulations, such as solutions, suspensions, and ointments, are commercially available. The bioadhesion technique can increase the therapy's effectiveness. The anti-bacterial, anti-carcinogenic, and wound-healing properties of herbal drugs are effective in the treatment for mouth ulcers. Compared to creams and ointments, the uses of herbal gels are more effective at pathological locations has the significant benefit of a quicker release of a medicine directly to the site of action. The herbal medicinal, plants are essential source of potentially useful active constituents for the development of therapeutic agents. Gel formulations have the potential to improve absorption characteristics and, consequently, the drug's bioavailability. This review focuses on causes, types of mouth ulcer, dosageforms, treatments, herbal remedies of mouth ulcer, advantages of gel, disadvantages of gel, formulation of gel, evaluation of gel.

Keywords:

Aphathous stomatitis, oral ulceration, Mouth Ulcer gel, Herbal gel.

INTRODUCTION

Aphthous stomatitis, another name for mouth ulcers, is a form of ulcerative disease that affects the oral mucosa and is characterized by recurrent sores on the throat and mouth. The inner layer of the cheek can be bit, food allergies, trauma, tooth brushing, hormonal changes, malnutrition, bacterial infections, causes mouth ulcers. They are uncomfortable, circular or oval lesions that mainly appear on the inside of the lips or cheeks.⁽¹⁾

A mouth ulcer occurs when the mucous membrane lining the inside of the mouth breaks or ruptures. Usually white or yellow in appearance, it mimics a mouth depression brought on by the mucous membrane. A break in the

epithelium's continuity brought on by molecular necrosis is referred to as an ulcer. Most often, ulcers develop in the oral area, for which the patient seeks dental or medical care. Pain, burning sensations, and/or redness are the most typical symptoms. Although they can develop in any part of the oral cavity, they become painful if they do so in the area that is movable. Quite common, mouth ulcers are typically caused by trauma, such as poorly fitted dentures, broken teeth or fillings.⁽²⁾

Any age group or population can develop a mouth ulcer. Mouth ulcers may also develop as a result of a number of serious, occasionally life-threatening illnesses, syndromes, and disorders. These include leukoplakia and oral cancer. Gum and oral sores that hurt are known as mouth ulcers. They are also known as canker sores. Even though the majority of mouth ulcers are not harmful, some people may find them extremely unpleasant, which can make it difficult to wash their teeth, eat, or drink. Depending on the type of ulcer, mouth ulcers can vary in size and in their symptoms.

CAUSES OF MOUTH ULCER

- Other foods those are high in acidity or spice, citrus fruits.
- Burns from hot beverages or food; irritation from chemicals in toothpaste or mouthwash.
- Biting one's tongue or chewing the insides of one's cheeks;
- Braces, poorly fitting dentures, and other mouth and gum-rubbing devices.
- Medications, such as beta-blockers and painkillers; anxiety or stress, and some genetic factors.⁽³⁾

TYPES OF MOUTH ULCERS

Minor ulcers: Approximately 80% of cases are minor aphthous ulcers, making them the most prevalent type. These usually go away in 10 to 2 weeks and have a diameter of 2 to 8 mm. These ulcers are often superficial in character, small in size, typically only 1 cm in diameter, few in number, appearing either alone or in groups, and healing without leaving any scars.

Major ulcers: About 10% of individuals develop major aphthous ulcers, the second type. These have a raised or uneven border and are larger and deeper in form, frequently measuring more than 1 cm in diameter. Additionally, they might appear as a single lesion or as several. Due to the degree of necrosis, this kind of ulcer may leave a scar inside the mouth and take many weeks to heal.

Herpetiform ulcers: This third category, which refers to the clustered appearance of lesions, is called herpetiform ulcers. A collection of dozens of tiny lesions, roughly the size of pinheads, make up this kind of ulcer. There is no connection between it and herpes virus infection.

These can number anywhere from 10 to 100 at a time and are made up of several little lesions that essentially merge together to form larger plaques. The ulcer may heal with a scar in 7 to 30 days, depending on its size and depth.⁽⁴⁾

Fig 1. Minor ulcer

Fig 2. Major ulcer

Fig 3. Herpetiform ulcer

VARIOUS DOSAGE FORMS USED TO TREAT MOUTH ULCER

- Toothpastes.
- Mouthwashes.
- Buccal tablets.
- Buccal patches.
- Medicated chewing gum.
- Medicinal gel.

1. Chlorhexidine mouth wash: Pain may be lessened by using mouthwash containing chlorhexidine (Corsodyl® or Chlorohex®). Additionally, it might speed up the healing of mouth ulcers. It aids in preventing the infection of mouth ulcers. Regrettably, it has no effect on the incidence of new ulcers. Typically, mouthwash containing chlorhexidine is used twice daily. If you use it frequently, your teeth may become discoloured. However, avoiding tannin-containing beverages (such tea, coffee, or red wine) and brushing your teeth before using them will help lessen the discolouration, which is typically not permanent. After brushing your teeth, thoroughly rinse your mouth since some toothpaste constituents can render chlorhexidine inactive.

2. Steroid lozenges: steroid lozenges (Corlan® pellets) may lessen discomfort and hasten the healing process of mouth ulcers. You can maintain a lozenge on an ulcer by applying pressure with your tongue until it dissolves. The sooner a steroid lozenge is started once an ulcer appears the better. It may 'nip it in the bud' and stop an ulcer from fully developing if taken early. One

lozenge taken four times a day is the standard dosage till the ulcer goes away. Utilize for a maximum of five days at a time.

3. **Protective, soothing pastes:** These products—like Orabase®—help to temporarily cover the ulcer in order to protect it.

4. **Painkilling oral rinse gel mouth spray:** Using a mouth spray, gel, or rinse that contains painkillers may help reduce discomfort. The effects of these painkillers are regrettably temporary. Pharmacies sell these products. For all of these products, pay close attention to the instructions on the packaging.

As examples, consider:

- Benzydamine mouthwash or spray (Diffiam®).

- Products that include Lidocaine, a local anesthetic that temporarily numbs the body.

- Bonjela® choline salicylate gel. Children under the age of sixteen should not take the adult form of Bonjela® since excessive use may cause Reye's syndrome. For the same reason, children should not take aspirin. Children's Bonjela® products have been reformulated using lidocaine instead of choline salicylate.⁽⁵⁾

HOME REMEDIES FOR THE TREATMENT OF MOUTH ULCER

Although mouth ulcers can be excruciating, there are a few easy at-home treatments that can reduce pain and up the healing process. These natural remedies offer calming, anti-inflammatory, or antibacterial qualities and are made with everyday home items.

1. Saltwater Rinse

To assist reduce swelling and sanitize the ulcer, dissolve a teaspoon of salt in warm water and rinse the mouth with it for 30 to 60 seconds. This treatment reduces inflammation, draws out extra fluid, and keeps the sore clean to avoid infection. Rinsing two or three times a day can help relieve pain and encourage recovery.

2. Honey

Relief may be obtained by topically applying a tiny quantity of honey to the ulcer.

Honey's inherent antibacterial and antiinflammatory qualities aid to keep the sore moist while easing pain and preventing infection.

For the most benefits, honey should be used raw or uncooked. Reapplying several times a day helps hasten the healing process.

3. Coconut Oil

Because coconut oil has antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties, applying it to the ulcer may be beneficial. By creating a barrier over the sore, it fights microorganisms and lessens food and drink irritation. Apply coconut oil multiple times a day and let it sit on the ulcer for a few minutes before swallowing for optimal effects

4. Aloe Vera Gel

The calming qualities of Aloe Vera are widely recognized .Applying fresh Aloe Vera gel to the ulcer can help it heal more quickly, kill bacteria, and lessen pain. Moreover, Aloe Vera contains cooling properties that may lessen discomfort .The best results come from using fresh aloe gel straight from the plant, but you can also use pure Aloe Vera gel from the shop.

5. Baking Soda Paste

To neutralise acidity and lessen discomfort, apply a thick paste made from modest amount of baking soda and water to the ulcer. This treatment works especially well for ulcers brought on by acidic foods or pH abnormalities in the mouth.

At first, it could sting a little, but it can help dry out the sore and speed up the healing process To neutralise acidity and lessen discomfort, apply a thick paste made from a modest amount of baking soda and water to the ulcer. This treatment works especially well for ulcers brought on by acidic foods or pH abnormalities in the mouth. At first, it could sting a little, but it can help dry out the sore and speed up the healing process.

6. Oil of Cloves

Eugenol, a naturally occurring painkiller with numbing and antimicrobial qualities, is found in clove oil. Using a cotton swab to apply a tiny amount can help ease discomfort and stop infections. To prevent irritation and achieve the greatest benefits, dilute the clove oil with carrier oil like coconut or olive oil.

7. Cubes of ice

Particularly for larger or more painful sores, applying an ice cube to the ulcer for a brief period of time might numb the region and temporarily relieve discomfort. This treatment is particularly beneficial for ulcers brought on by discomfort from dentures or braces. Before applying the ice, wrap it in a clean cloth to help shield delicate tissues from direct harm.

8. Paste with Turmeric

Turmeric contains potent antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities. Pain, oedema, and bacterial development can be decreased by putting a thick paste made from turmeric powder and water or honey to the ulcer. Its effects can be amplified by leaving it on for a few minutes before washing it off.

9. Yoghurt

Consuming plain yoghurt containing live probiotics helps lower the risk of recurring ulcers by balancing the bacteria in the mouth and digestive tract. Probiotics help maintain gut health, which is important for immune response and inflammation management. Regularly consuming yoghurt could help stop outbreaks in the future.⁽⁶⁾

Herbal Remedies for mouth ulcer

Photogenic agents are plant-based substances that have traditionally been used by herbalists and indigenous healers to prevent and treat ulcers. These agents are derived from various plants that contain bioactive compounds, which can help heal and soothe the stomach lining, reduce inflammation, and fight off infections. Botanical compounds with anti-ulcer activity are derived from various plant species and have been extensively studied for their ability to treat and prevent gastric ulcers. These compounds include flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and gums and mucilages, which have been shown to reduce inflammation, protect the stomach lining, and promote healing

Herbal drugs have long been used in ethno medical systems for the treatment and prevention of gastric ulcers. Among these, licorice, aloe gel, and capsicum (chili) are some of the most commonly utilized plants, with numerous studies supporting their therapeutic potential.

Advantages of herbal medicines

- Herbal remedies frequently offer a natural, all-encompassing method of medical treatment. Instead of concentrating on specific ailments, they frequently treat the body as a whole. Many herbs have multiple therapeutic effects that address the root causes of illness, rather than just alleviating symptoms.
- Comparing herbal remedies to pharmaceutical medications, the former typically have fewer and milder adverse effects. This is because they are derived from plants and usually contain a broad range of compounds that work in harmony with the body.

- Herbal remedies are frequently less expensive than name-brand medications. The cost can be further decreased by growing several herbs in home gardens. Additionally, they are generally accessible in a variety of forms, including tinctures, teas, and capsules.
- The immune system is known to be strengthened and supported by a variety of herbs. Better general health and an enhanced capacity to fend off infections may result from this.
- Many herbs can act as preventative measures, supporting the body before illness strikes. This is a central principle in many traditional medical systems, including Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and Ayurveda.

HERBS USED FOR THE TREATMENT OF MOUTH ULCER

- **Aloe Vera**

Family-*Liliaceae*

Mechanism of action-It speeds up the healing process while easing the discomfort and irritation brought on by mouth ulcers. How it works: By creating a protective barrier over the ulcer, Aloevera gel helps lessen additional irritation from contact, food, and beverages. Additionally, it contains substances like *acemannan* that lessen inflammation and encourage tissue regeneration.

Uses

- Anti- inflammatory.
- Antibacterial.
- Wound healing.

2. Licorice

Family- *Fabaceae*.

Mechanism of action- Licorice root contains *Glycyrrhizin*, which is thought to have soothing properties that can relieve the irritation caused by mouth ulcers. It can also form a protective film over the ulcer to aid in healing.

Uses

- Anti-inflammatory.
- Anti-microbial.
- Help to alleviate pain and prevent secondary infections in mouth ulcer.

3. Turmeric

Family- *Zingiberaceae*.

Mechanism of action- Turmeric's *Curcumin* has the ability to block the inflammatory processes that lead to ulcer development. To aid with healing, it can be used as a mouthwash or applied directly as a paste.

Uses

- Anti-inflammatory.
- Anti-oxidant compound that is beneficial for reducing the pain and swelling associated with mouth ulcer.

4. Clove

Family- *Myrtaceae*.

Mechanism of action- To ease pain and lessen inflammation, clove oil can be administered directly to the ulcer. Because of its antimicrobial qualities, subsequent infections can be avoided.

Uses

- Analgesic.
- Anti-bacterial.
- Helps to relieving the pain and preventing infections associated with Mouth ulcer.⁽⁷⁾

5. HONEY

Family-*Apidae*.

Mechanism of action- Because honey has antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities, it can be applied to mouth ulcers to reduce inflammation and kill oral germs, which in turn helps the ulcer heal itself.

Uses

- It is used to heal oral ulcers since it exhibits antioxidant action.
- It is also used to treat cancer because it exhibits apoptotic action and antibacterial activity, which eliminates oral microorganisms.
- It is also used to treat diabetes because of its anti-inflammatory properties, which reduce oral inflammation.
- In addition to being used to treat cardiovascular disease, honey also helps alleviate asthma.

6. MINT

Family-*Lamiaceae*.

Mechanism of action- When applied to a mouth ulcer, mint leaves provide a cooling effect that reduces ulcer discomfort and leaves the mouth smelling nice.

Uses

- It has antibacterial properties against cryogenic bacteria
- It has antimicrobial properties, which is why it is used to treat ulcers
- The presence of flavonoids in mint leaves helps to promote fresh breath; and it has a cooling effect on the mouth.⁽⁸⁾

7. GUAVA

Family- *Myrtaceae*.

Mechanism of action - Guava, rich in *flavonoids*, *tannins*, and *vitamin C*, exerts anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects. These actions reduce pain, prevent infection, and promote tissue healing in mouth ulcers. Its astringent properties also form a protective layer over the ulcer.

Uses

- Antioxidant.
- Antifungal.
- Anticancer.
- Antibacterial.
- Anti-inflammatory.

8. CHAMOMILLA

Family- *Daisy.*

Mechanism of action - Chamomile contains active compounds like *chamazulene*, *apigenin*, and *bisabolol* with strong anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. These reduce pain, swelling, and bacterial growth at the ulcer site. It also promotes mucosal healing through antioxidant and mild analgesic effects.

Uses

- Antispasmodic.
- Antiviral.
- Antibacterial.
- Antifungal.
- Anti-inflammatory.

9. NEEM

Family- *Meliaceae.*

Mechanism of action- Neem helps heal mouth ulcers through its anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties, reducing pain and preventing infection. Its antioxidants promote tissue repair by reducing oxidative stress. Additionally, Neem enhances immune response, speeding up ulcer healing.

Uses

- Antioxidant.
- Antifungal.
- Antibacterial.
- Anti-inflammatory.
- Antiulcer.⁽⁹⁾

PHARMACEUTICAL GEL

A gel is a solid or semisolid system consisting of two or more constituents with a condensed bulk and liquid interpenetration. Although gels and jellies include a little number of particles dispersed throughout a large volume of liquid, their consistency is more solid than liquid. One characteristic that sets jelly and gel apart is the existence of some kind of epidermal structure, which gives them their solid-like properties.

ADVANTAGES OF GEL

- Avoid the first-pass metabolism.
- It is easy to implement, convenient, and acceptable.
- The capacity to more accurately deliver medications to a designated area.
- Making it possible to employ medications with a short biological half-life.
- Enhancing the medication's pharmacological and physiological effects.
- Improving patient compliance.
- Self-medication is possible.
- Preventing intravenous therapy's hazards and disadvantages, as well as the different conditions of absorption, like pH fluctuations and the presence of enzymes.
- It is easy to terminate the medication.

DISADVANTAGES OF GEL

- People with contact dermatitis may have skin irritation from the drug and/or excipients.
- Certain drugs may cause allergic reactions because of their limited permeability through the skin or mucous membranes.
- Used exclusively for medications that needs extremely low plasma concentrations to work.
- An enzyme found in the epidermis may denature drugs.
- It is more difficult for drugs with larger particle sizes to be absorbed through skin.⁽¹⁰⁾

USES OF GEL

- As medication delivery methods for drugs that are taken orally.
- To provide a topical drug to the eyes, mucous membranes, or skin.
- Dental care preventive gels, such as phosphoric acid gel and sodium fluoride gel.
- Gels as catheter lubricants.⁽¹¹⁾

FORMULATION OF GEL

A specified quantity of Carbopol 934 was continuously stirred while being dissolved in the necessary volume of distilled water. After 5 milliliters of distilled water had cooled, propylene glycol was added, and the necessary amounts of methyl and propyl paraben were dissolved by boiling on a water bath. The aforesaid combination was further combined with powdered herbal extracts at different concentrations, and the volume was increased to 20 milliliters using distilled water.

Triethanolamine was then added drop wise to the mixture to adjust the necessary pH after all the ingredients had been well combined and stirred continuously in the Carbopol 934 gel.⁽¹²⁾

PREPARATION OF HERBAL GEL

Carbapol 934 mixed in demineralized water.

Take 5ml distilled water + methyl paraben and propyl paraben.

Warm in water bath.

Add propylene glycol when it as cooled.

Then add different concentration of different types of powder herbs or extract.

Mixed all ingredients and add Carbopal 934.

With Continous Stirring, Gradually Add Triethanolamine to adjust pH to the desired level.⁽¹³⁾

EVALUATION OF GEL

1. Visual Appearance

Colour, clarity, texture, transparency, and the presence of any gritty particles were all checked in the created gels.

2. Measurement of pH

A digital pH meter was used to measure the herbal gel compositions' pH. One gramme of gel was taken, mixed with ten milliliters of distilled water, and left for two hours. The formulation's pH was measured three times, and the average results are shown. The gel formulation's pH was specified.

3. Homogeneity

After the gels were poured into the container, established gel compositions were examined visually to determine their homogeneity. They were examined to determine whether any aggregate masses were present and how they looked.

4. Spreadability

Spread ability is defined as the number of seconds it takes for two slides to separate from gel that is positioned between them when a specific weight is applied. If two slides can be separated in less time, the spread ability will be better.

Spread ability is calculated by using the formula:

$$S=ML/T$$

Where,

M-weight tied to upper slide.

L-length of glass slides.

T- Time taken to separate the slides.

5. Viscosity

The measurement of viscosity of the formulated gel was determined by Brookfield Viscometer with spindle no. 1 at 25°C. The gels were rotated at speed 0.3, 0.6 and 1.5 rotations per minute and at each speed, the corresponding dial reading was noted. Then viscosity of the prepared gels was obtained by multiplication of the dial reading with factor given in the Brookfield Viscometer catalogues.

6. Extrudability

The gel formulations were evaluated for extrudability by filling them in collapsible aluminum tubes, sealing the ends, and recording their weight. The tubes were then placed between two glass slides, clamped, and subjected to a 500gm weight. The extruded gel was collected and weighed to determine the percentage of gel extruded.

7. Wash ability

The washability of the gel formulation was evaluated by applying it to the skin and checking the ease of washing with water. This assessment determines how easily the gel can be removed from the skin.

8. Mucoadhesive Studies

Mucoadhesive properties were evaluated by coating glass plates with polymer and immersing them in a temperature-controlled mucous solution. The force required to pull the plate out of the solution was measured under constant conditions to determine the mucoadhesive strength.

9. Gel strength

The weight's penetration time in seconds into the gel was used to calculate the gel's strength. Five grammes of each of the optimized batches were sampled, and 3.5 grammes of weight were applied to the gel's surface. The weight's penetration time in seconds through 0.5 cm of gel.

10. Antimicrobial Activity

To make agar plate media, 28 grammes of nutritional agar powder were added to one liter of distilled water. The mixture was then heated to dissolve all of the ingredients. For 15 minutes, the dissolved liquid is autoclaved at 1210 C to allow it to cool without hardening. After that, inoculation the microbe is placed in nutrient agar medium and allowed to solidify on plates. Then, using a borer, make holes in the same medium that are roughly 9 mm in diameter using the agar well diffusion method. Orange peel extract antibacterial solution was poured straight into the perforations. After being incubated, the plates are reported.⁽¹⁴⁾

CONCLUSION

The formulation of herbal gels for their exceptional bioadhesion, site-specific drug administration, and simplicity of use, herbal gels stand out among other dosage forms. These gels, which are made with natural extracts and mucoadhesive ingredients like Carbopol 934, guarantee prolonged contact with the ulcer site, increasing their effectiveness. Bypassing first-pass metabolism, lowering systemic adverse effects, and enhancing patient compliance are some of their benefits. The efficacy of herbal gels is supported by the evaluation parameters, which include pH, viscosity, spread ability, and antibacterial activity. All things considered, creating and applying herbal gels to treat mouth ulcers offers a potentially effective treatment alternative that blends conventional herbal knowledge with contemporary pharmaceutical methods. Their position in the mainstream of oral healthcare will be further cemented by additional research and clinical confirmation.

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